

Human–Computer Metacognition: Visualizing LLM Reasoning to Support Independent Confidence Judgments

Antonia Schlieder
antonia.schlieder@iwr.uni-heidelberg.de
Heidelberg University
Heidelberg, Germany

Jan Rummel
jan.rummel@psychologie.uni-heidelberg.de
Heidelberg University
Heidelberg, Germany

Filip Sadlo
sadlo@uni-heidelberg.de
Heidelberg University
Heidelberg, Germany

Figure 1: AI literacy is the ability to make informed AI-delegation decisions. It involves evaluating an LLM’s capabilities in relation to a given task, a process that can be understood as a form of human–computer metacognition (a). Visual cues that enrich text with conditional highlighting and Euler diagrams can support users in monitoring the reasoning of an LLM. The visualization represents logical relationships, removing misleading linguistic surface features in the process (b).

Abstract

AI literacy requires users to make informed decisions about which tasks to delegate to AI systems. We propose that independently assessing an AI system’s capabilities is a form of interpersonal metacognition, which we call human–computer metacognition. Building on recent work regarding the intrapersonal metacognitive demands of generative AI, we introduce a framework that distinguishes four dimensions of metacognition in human–AI collaboration. Since large language models (LLMs) produce text that sounds plausible regardless of its accuracy, independently evaluating the LLM’s reasoning abilities is essential for AI literacy. We outline how visualization can support this metacognitive monitoring. As a case study, we demonstrate how sequential visual cues can represent explanations of logical reasoning tasks generated by LLMs in a form that removes linguistic surface features, enabling step-by-step evaluation of the reasoning chain.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Visualization; Human computer interaction (HCI).**

Keywords

Visualization literacy, AI literacy, metacognition, visual cues, human–AI collaboration

1 Introduction

Literacy refers to a set of skills that a community considers indispensable for managing tasks in everyday life and work. The domains for which forms of literacy are identified are expanding steadily. In addition to the basic skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic, a core set of competencies has been identified, comprising scientific [9], media [25], financial [28], health [32], and visualization literacy [16, 31]. More recently, AI literacy [22, 26] has been added to this list. What these efforts share are two things: they define a core set of skills and use autonomy as a key criterion. The identified competencies are intended to enable individuals to make appropriate decisions in commonly occurring situations without guidance from a third party.

AI literacy occupies a special position in this context, insofar as AI is a universal assistance technology that can replace literacy in the other areas mentioned—but at the cost of a loss of personal autonomy. A concept of AI literacy that balances assistance and autonomy must take into account the relationship between human and machine learning. This applies particularly to the rapidly increasing use in everyday life of the support that large language models (LLMs) offer in chat mode [10]. Even though users are often unaware of this, they are constantly making decisions about which tasks to assign to the LLM and which to solve themselves.

In this position paper, we examine a challenge of AI literacy from the perspective of metacognition research. More specifically, we ask how visualizations can be used to support individuals in tracing solutions to logical inference problems generated by LLMs. Put simply, metacognition refers to the ability to reflect on one’s

own thinking (*intrapersonal*) or the thinking of others (*interpersonal*) [42]. Within the discipline of visualization, there has been a growing interest in the metacognitive processes related to visual reasoning [5, 6, 34]. Recent work by Tankelevitch et al. [37] has examined the metacognitive demands that generative AI places on users, emphasizing intrapersonal metacognition. While they acknowledge that “*confidence in the system’s abilities is also important, and likely interacts with self-confidence*”, they primarily focus on self-confidence because it aligns with the traditional intrapersonal definition of metacognition. We focus on the lesser-considered metacognitive perspective on confidence in AI and argue that the user’s assessment of whether an LLM can solve a task without errors is central to AI literacy. We will show that this means to expand the scope of metacognition from intrapersonal to inter-actor processes [7, 20, 29]. For successful collaboration, users must actively monitor and evaluate the AI’s reasoning and capabilities when delegating tasks, a process we call *human–computer metacognition*.

Introducing this additional metacognitive dimension to consider for AI literacy constitutes the first contribution of this paper (1 (a)). The second contribution lies in exploring how human–computer metacognition can be supported. We propose an environment for studying how visual cues that enrich text can help users evaluate LLM-generated reasoning chains and logical inferences (1 (b)). We conclude with open research questions related to human–computer metacognition and discuss how this environment allows us to investigate them.

2 Human–Computer Metacognition for AI Literacy

A key component of AI literacy is deciding which types of tasks a human user can confidently delegate to an AI system [2]. We argue that the cognitive mechanisms involved in this decision can be considered within the conceptual framework of metacognition since they involve, among other things, evaluating the system’s ability to perform a given task correctly.

2.1 Metacognition, Learning, and Literacy: Evidence from Visual Reasoning

Metacognition refers to the processes by which cognitive activity is monitored and regulated, including during reasoning [1, 13, 30]. In the context of visualization, metacognitive processes operate in a feedback loop between object-level activities—such as decoding visual elements, detecting patterns, or making visuospatial inferences—and a meta level that evaluates these activities and selects visual reasoning strategies. Information about perceived effort, uncertainty, or potential errors during visualization use is passed to the meta level as metacognitive knowledge (*meta-knowledge*). Based on this knowledge, the meta level exerts metacognitive control (*meta-control*) by activating, adapting, or inhibiting strategies for interpreting the visualization, thereby shaping subsequent visual reasoning [34].

We illustrate the interaction between metacognition and learning using a well-studied example from visualization research [8, 27]: the interpretation of a bar chart with a truncated *y*-axis. This task requires viewers to consider the axis values in addition to bar lengths

when making comparisons between data points. Being able to recognize this and solve such deceptive visualization tasks is one aspect of visualization literacy [15]. Previous work [34] examined how metacognition relates to understanding misleading visualizations. The authors found that viewers who were tasked to answer questions with such deceptive bar charts could not strictly be classified into those who know to check the *y*-axis and always answer correctly versus those who do not. Instead, a form of learning was observed. After initially comparing only bar heights and answering the first few tasks incorrectly, participants adapted successful reasoning strategies that involved reading off axis values. This adaptation was entirely self-regulated, since there was no feedback given on the correctness of their answers. Through coding participants’ strategy descriptions for meta-knowledge and meta-control, it was shown that the resulting improvement of accuracy over time directly correlates with metacognitive skills. People with higher metacognitive awareness adapted their strategies after assessing that their initial reasoning was flawed without the need for any external feedback.

This example illustrates that intrapersonal metacognition is a fundamental component of acquiring literacy in a given domain. Someone who is visualization-literate is able to detect errors in their reasoning more quickly and correct their behavior. In other words, visualization literacy involves having metacognitive awareness, that is, knowing when and how to apply *one’s own* skills appropriately.

2.2 From Intrapersonal to Inter-Actor Metacognition in Reasoning Tasks

The metacognitive processes involved in visualization literacy are intrapersonal in nature. They concern thinking about one’s own thinking. Conversely, literacy in collaborative settings requires interpersonal metacognition [7, 20], which is knowing when and how to leverage *others’* skills appropriately. When humans collaborate with AI systems, this interpersonal metacognition must extend beyond human-to-human interaction. We introduce the notion of human–computer metacognition, by which we mean the metacognitive monitoring and evaluation of AI systems’ capabilities to determine when and how to appropriately delegate tasks to them.

Interpersonal metacognition expands on intrapersonal metacognition by taking into account our assessment of others’ thinking [7, 29]. Evaluating others’ knowledge, beliefs, and resources is crucial for decision-making in social situations [14]. For instance, in collaborative learning settings [19], interpersonal metacognition is particularly prevalent when working on problems with a high difficulty level.

We propose to distinguish four dimensions of metacognitive activity in human–AI collaboration (Figure 2). The user monitors and controls themselves in a loop of *intrapersonal metacognition*. Similarly, the AI system possesses a form of self-monitoring, for example through confidence scores, which we refer to as *intra-computer metacognition*. There are two sides to inter-actor metacognition when humans work with AI. When evaluating the AI system’s capabilities based on its output, the user employs *human–computer metacognition*. The framework in Figure 2 also allows for a kind of *computer-human metacognition*, that makes the AI monitor and

Figure 2: Four intra- and inter-actor metacognitive processes in human-AI collaboration. Human-computer metacognition that involves assessing the AI system’s abilities, has to be supported for promoting AI literacy.

adapt to the perceived user’s skills, which closes the metacognitive loop between human and computer. We acknowledge that applying the term metacognition to the computer-side dimensions requires some conceptual leeway, as whether AI systems genuinely possess metacognitive abilities remains an open question tied to broader debates about theory of mind in AI [18]. However, the human-side dimensions, particularly human-computer metacognition, do not depend on resolving this question.

In human-AI collaboration, intrapersonal metacognition involves assessing how confident the user is in completing a given task with only their own skills [40] and monitoring how AI-generated answers influence one’s decision-making process [21].

AI systems exhibit intra-computer metacognition in the sense that they can offer confidence judgments to users in the form of numerical confidence scores or probability estimates [46]. When collaborating with LLMs on a task, the models can offer verbalized confidence judgments [44] to supplement their answers. While such judgments provide an easy-to-compute and easy-to-understand measure to assess generated answers, they are only beneficial to the user if they are trustworthy, i.e., if the confidence score matches the accuracy of the answer. Critically, for benchmarks that assess logical reasoning skills [24], the LLMs tested by Yang et al. [44] were particularly poorly calibrated, with confidence scores deviating around 40 % from the models’ true accuracy on average. In addition to the overconfidence problem that poses a significant risk for reliable LLM-supported decision-making [17], LLMs produce fluent, plausible-sounding answers [23] and explanations [45] regardless of correctness. Users cannot rely on linguistic surface features, such as the level of detail or fluency, to verify LLM-generated responses [38].

Given that LLMs’ projected confidence can be misleading, human-computer metacognition becomes particularly critical. Users must develop independent metacognitive monitoring of LLM outputs. Knowing when to trust, verify, or reject LLM reasoning is necessary for making informed delegation decisions. In this sense, human-computer metacognition extends the work of Tankelevitch et al. on intrapersonal metacognitive demands of generative AI [37]. By adopting an interpersonal metacognitive perspective, we integrate assessments of the AI system’s skills into a unified framework with intra- and inter-actor dimensions (Figure 2), providing a more complete account of metacognition in human-AI collaboration. This framework opens new opportunities for designing support systems

that enhance human-computer metacognition beyond traditional self-monitoring.

For the sake of completeness, we will briefly mention the fourth dimension: computer-human metacognition. One can consider how an AI system’s monitoring of the user’s thinking might affect the system’s behavior. For instance, the system could adapt the complexity of explanations to a learner’s assessed skill level in a tutoring setting. However, this is beyond the scope of the paper.

3 An Environment for Monitoring LLM Reasoning with Visual Cues

In order to enhance human-computer metacognition, collaboration environments must provide users with the ability to independently evaluate LLM capabilities. We outline how visualization can provide this support while mitigating the effects of linguistic fluency and projected confidence on users’ metacognitive judgments of LLM reasoning.

3.1 Task Domain

As a case study, we focus on monitoring LLMs’ logical reasoning skills, specifically their ability to make valid inferences about conditional “if-then” statements. Being able to verify arguments is a skill needed in all areas of decision-making, not just AI literacy. Logical reasoning is also the task domain for which accuracy and confidence of LLMs deviate the most [44]. Figure 3 (left) shows an example of such a task [24], where a text passage describes a conditional statement and a flawed inference made from that statement. In brief, Hank states that *if it does not rain, then he will go climbing*, which Jimmy falsely interprets to mean that *if it rains, then Hank will not go climbing*. Without going into the details of conditional propositional logic, Jimmy’s blaming of Hank represents a common formal fallacy (denial of the antecedent) [3, 4]. Therefore, of the four answer options, option B, “Jimmy’s reasoning is illogical”, is the appropriate comment.

LLMs are often tasked to produce reasoning chains, both to explain their thinking to the user and as a prompting technique to improve output accuracy [41, 43]. This step-by-step thinking takes the form of continuous, plausible-sounding prose, which can make tracing an argument’s logical structure cognitively demanding for the user. In the case of the example task in Figure 3, GPT-4o incorrectly selects option C as the answer and offers a fluent but flawed

explanation (Figure 3 left). It is difficult to detect that the explanation is logically unsound from the generated text alone, as the verbal fluency masks the logical flaw. However, the steps of conditional logic embedded in the text can be extracted and represented in a form that makes the logical structure more transparent.

3.2 Visual Cue Design

A visual representation of the logical inferences made in an LLM-generated explanation has two key advantages. First, it presents information in a modality that eliminates all linguistic surface features that could cloud a person’s judgment of the LLM’s reasoning. Second, visualizing each step of the reasoning chain separately allows users to evaluate each logical transition rather than making a holistic judgment about the entire argument. This step-by-step monitoring allows for better error localization and more calibrated confidence assessments.

We implement this approach by adapting the sequential visual cue (SVC) framework [35], which was originally developed to provide step-by-step hints in visual reasoning tasks. We use SVCs to show how the logical structure of textual reasoning chains develops, taking advantage of the attention-guiding properties of visual cues in text to support better cognitive resource allocation [39].

Figure 3 illustrates how this approach to monitoring LLM-generated reasoning is applied to the example task. We employ Euler diagrams [11, 33] to visualize conditionals as set relationships. In an Euler diagram, the “if” (antecedent) and “then” (consequent) parts of a conditional statement are represented as sets (circles), and their spatial relationships indicate logical relationships. Overlapping sets indicate possible co-occurrence; nested sets, implication; and disjoint sets, mutual exclusion.

As SVCs, each conditional statement in the text is marked by highlighting the antecedent and consequent (negations are underlined), and linked to its corresponding Euler diagram. For clarity, text highlighting and diagrams use matching color schemes. In the flawed explanation, two conditional statements occur. First, the LLM restates what Hank said, “If it doesn’t rain tomorrow, then I’ll go climbing,” and then reinterprets it as “he would only refrain from climbing if it rained.” In the text, these two statements are presented as equivalent, and the subsequent explanation builds on this assumption. However, the corresponding Euler diagrams reveal the critical reasoning error: the two conditionals do not have the same logical structure. This is evident in the different spatial relationships in the two diagrams. The first diagram shows that rain (R) and climbing (C) can co-occur, which is Hank’s original statement. The second diagram, however, shows rain (R) and climbing (C) as disjoint, which is the incorrect inference made by the LLM.

3.3 Studying Human–Computer Metacognition

Augmenting the LLM-generated explanation with the proposed visual cues enables users to monitor reasoning without being influenced by the LLM’s projected confidence. Users can verify each step of the logical inference and calibrate their metacognitive judgments step by step.

The monitoring environment enables us to closely study users’ human–computer metacognition during LLM-assisted logical reasoning. In user studies designed for this purpose, participants

are presented with logical reasoning tasks together with LLM-generated explanations (Figure 3). These explanations are supplemented with visual cues in the intervention condition and without cues in the baseline condition. Instead of solving the tasks themselves, participants evaluate the LLM’s reasoning by providing a retrospective confidence rating of the correctness of the LLM’s answer. Participants can then act on this judgment by adopting the LLM’s answer or deferring. Incorrectly adopting an answer incurs a penalty. This setup operationalizes human–computer metacognition directly: it is measured by the extent to which confidence in the LLM’s answer reflects its actual correctness. Importantly, well-calibrated confidence may be a necessary but not sufficient condition for making the correct decision—a participant must not only feel uncertain about an incorrect answer, but also act on that uncertainty by deferring. This allows us to examine human–computer metacognition and its effect on delegation decisions separately. We discuss specific research hypotheses in Section 4.2.

4 Discussion

In human–AI collaboration, the independent assessment of LLM capabilities is essential for successful task delegation and therefore AI literacy. Building on previous work on intrapersonal metacognition in the context of generative AI [37], we adopted an interpersonal metacognitive lens to argue that actively monitoring and evaluating AI reasoning constitutes another metacognitive dimension, that of human–computer metacognition.

We have outlined how an environment that uses visualization to monitor LLMs’ logical reasoning can support users in their confidence judgments of the system’s abilities, without being misguided by its linguistic fluency or verbalized confidence. Translating the LLM’s explanations into logical Euler diagrams and enriching the text with conditional highlighting makes the separate logical transitions of generated reasoning chains explicit and traceable.

4.1 Limitations

While essential, human–computer metacognition is one of several factors that inform delegation decisions. The four metacognitive dimensions of human–AI collaboration proposed here need to be developed further to explore how they relate to other concepts of human–AI collaboration such as trust, reliance, and agency.

One might argue that as LLM performance continues to improve, that, just as we rarely question whether a calculator’s arithmetic is correct, the need to actively monitor their capabilities will diminish. However, this overlooks a fundamental distinction: unlike arithmetic operations with objectively correct answers, language is inherently ambiguous, particularly in the domain of logical reasoning about natural language text. The “Great Rationality Debate” [12, 36] that centers on the tension between descriptive (how people actually think) and normative (how people should think) accounts of rationality, illustrates this challenge. Since humans have not reached a consensus on normative standards for reasoning about ambiguous language, LLMs’ interpretations cannot be definitively considered correct. This makes human–computer metacognition essential, even as technical performance improves.

Figure 3: Example task [24] (left) and GPT-4o's flawed explanation augmented with Euler diagrams and text highlighting as sequential visual cues (right). Color-coded highlighting marks "if" (purple) and "then" (green) parts of conditional statements. The diagrams reveal the logical error: the two conditionals have different structures despite being presented as equivalent.

4.2 Future Work

The consideration of human-computer metacognition raises several open research questions, two of which we would like to highlight and discuss how they can be investigated using the monitoring environment with visual cues described in Section 3.

Although the four metacognitive dimensions in our framework interact with each other, the nature and effects of these interactions in human-LLM collaboration are unclear. For example, how does a user's intrapersonal self-confidence interact with their confidence in the LLM's reasoning? The proposed monitoring environment enables investigation of this question by collecting retrospective confidence judgments on the user's reasoning and the LLM's reasoning, which can be compared against actual correctness. These established metacognitive measures can reveal interaction patterns and inform the design of visual cues that enhance human-computer metacognition.

Previous findings on individual differences in metacognitive skills and visual reasoning abilities raise the question of differential effects: Do users with stronger intrapersonal metacognitive skills also demonstrate stronger human-computer metacognitive skills? If these skills are correlated, visual support may primarily benefit those who already self-monitor effectively. However, if they are independent, then visual cues that adapt to the user's metacognitive skills may be necessary.

5 Conclusion

This position paper introduces the concept of human-computer metacognition as a critical dimension of AI literacy. It extends metacognitive processes beyond traditional self-monitoring to include the independent evaluation of AI reasoning capabilities. We outline how visual representations of LLM reasoning, specifically sequential visual cues, support this metacognitive activity by removing misleading linguistic features and enabling step-by-step verification of logical validity. Our proposed four-dimensional framework provides a conceptual basis for understanding the cognitive processes necessary for making informed decisions about delegating tasks to AI.

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